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**The Sanctity of Human Life in Numbers
35:30-31: A Biblical Response to
Bloodshed in Nigeria**

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Abstract

The present wave of bloodshed in Nigeria has caused global concern, eroding the peace and tranquillity that citizens deserve, and turning villages, cities, and states into war zones. Despite the alarming situation, the government and citizens seem powerless to stop this evil tide. Therefore, this research investigated whether provocation or intention regarding killing a human being is justifiable from Numbers 35:30-31. This was then applied to cases of bloodshed in Nigeria (Global Conflict Tracker, 2021). Although there are written discourses on the economic, socio-cultural, family, political and spiritual impact of violent attacks on society, the paper seeks to contribute to the body of knowledge as it explores the biblical response to bloodshed in Nigeria from Numbers 35:30-31. Through making deductions from Johann August Ernesti's historical-grammatical method of exegesis and administering a questionnaire to one hundred and twenty-three respondents randomly selected from the six geo-political zones of the country, findings show that there is no regard for human lives by perpetrators of bloodshed. They also believe in the sanctity of human lives and would not violate life unless it is extremely necessary. Also, from the exegesis, Provocation and intention do not justify the killing of another person, as it negates the sanctity of human life. Therefore, the study recommends that citizens pursue love, care, compassion, and tolerance attributes. Parents

should instil the right traits and culture from home. Security forces should deploy measures to control crime and criminal behaviour in society. Political leaders and politicians need not use religion to divide citizens or encourage the breakdown of law and order. Religious leaders should encourage intra- and inter-faith dialogue and teachings that advocate peace. The government should avoid acts of injustice, inequality, and abuse of human rights that provoke victims to embark on a killing spree.

Keywords: Bloodshed, Provocation, Tolerance, Government, Citizens, Numbers 35:30-31

Introduction

The surge of bloodletting has reached its peak in Nigeria. The relative peace and tranquillity that permeated the atmosphere before now has been violated, and the violence has graduated into gruesome cases of murder and shedding of blood in diverse manners. Besides murder, lives are lost due to ritual killing, unresolved land disputes between individuals and families and other lawless acts. In Nigeria, religious crises, including social, political, and ethnic violence, are the leading causes of the death of innocent people. The motivation for this study stems from the fact that so much blood has been shed, through murder, manslaughter, assassination and ritual killing. It is still being shed almost daily that the list of atrocities cannot be exhausted. In July 2016, Nigerians woke up to the news of the murder of Mrs Eunice Elisha, a deaconess at the Divine Touch Parish of the Redeemed Christian Church of God, a mother of seven. She was killed by unknown assailants while preaching in Kubwa, Abuja, a Federal Capital Territory satellite (Adepegba, 2021). Newspapers are replete with news of kidnappings. In 2020, 937 people were reported to have been kidnapped in Kaduna State alone (Ibekwe & Alabi, 2021). In the first half of 2021, 2,371 persons were abducted across the 36 states of the federation, including the FCT, and around 10 billion naira was demanded as ransom for the victims. Reporting the states with the highest number of victims and death cases, Agbakwuru and Wuyo (2021) revealed that in Niger State, 58 people were killed out of 643 victims in 28 kidnap incidents; Zamfara State had 22 people killed out of 519 victims; Kaduna had 41 deaths out of 360 victims in 26 incidents. Schools were also targeted, with over 500 students kidnapped. One of the most recent was the abduction of 121 pupils of Bethel Baptist Secondary School in Damishi, Kaduna State. Further, some locations and

roads have become death traps, dens and hide-outs for kidnappers that citizens are now more conscious of than highway robbers.

Unfortunately, Reverend Lawan Andimi did not live to share the story of his ordeal in the captivity of Boko Haram insurgents. He was a Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) State Chairman in the Michika Local Government Area of Northeastern Adamawa State. He was kidnapped on the 3rd January 2020, in a raid on the town, a key town on the Cameroon border. After negotiations with his family members for ransom broke down, his captors threatened to kill him and eventually carried it out. A live video of him being kept in a hole and butchered like a ram, with blood oozing out of his body till he died, was circulated (Olatunji, Onyedika and Daka, 2021). The motivation for the study stems from the fact that so much blood has been shed and is still being shed daily that the list of atrocities cannot be exhausted. The disturbing point is the degree of intentionality, coordination and degrading manners in which these grievous crimes occur. Therefore, this research investigated whether provocation or intention regarding killing a human being is justifiable from Numbers 35:30-31. This was then applied to cases of bloodshed in Nigeria (Global Conflict Tracker, 2021). Although there are written discourses on the economic, socio-cultural, family, political and spiritual impact of violent attacks on society, the paper seeks to contribute to the body of knowledge as it explores the biblical response to bloodshed in Nigeria from Numbers 35:30-31. Johann August Ernesti's historical-grammatical method of exegesis was employed because the Bible is an ancient sacred text written within human history in the ancient world, with a cultural gap that significantly differs from the twenty-first century. The method uses the history and grammar of the text to draw out the interpretation for the original and contemporary readers. Simple descriptive statistics were also used to analyse the opinions of respondents. This study argues that an interpretation and application of Numbers 35:30-31 can serve as a veritable instrument to respond to the menace of bloodshed in Nigerian society. This paper discusses the perspectives of bloodshed in Nigeria and an appropriate response to it.

Overview of Bloodshed in Nigeria

Bloodshed has been described as the killing or causing the death of another person(s). It also means diminishing the natural lifespan of another person (Tams, Berster and Schiffbauer, 2014:79). Olaniyan (2016: 19) opined that

people view the subject of bloodshed from different points of view. He noted that blood in human veins is the same in composition irrespective of race, colour, language and tribe. According to him, blood has the same value as human existence, so it is the life of all living creatures and, therefore, sacred. He admitted that despite its value, shedding human blood is a universal phenomenon. Bloodshed takes various forms and falls into different categories. There are, for instance, excusable, justifiable and legal deaths, as there are those that are not. Deaths and killings are defined variously by other factors such as the gender or age of the victim involved.

Bloodshed in present-day Nigeria has become a regular occurrence and appears with no end in sight. In his article, Jegede (2014: 125-129) gave an abridged history of violence in Nigeria. He noted that blood had been spilt due to the greed and selfishness of past and present leaders in Nigeria, even though the independence of the country was achieved without bloodshed. He stated that bloodshed reared its ugly head in the first military coup, where Tafawa Balewa and a few other prominent leaders were murdered on January 14-15, 1966. The second coup on July 29, 1966, claimed the life of Aguiyi-Ironsi, and many Easterners in the North were massacred. This led to the declaration of the Eastern region as the Independent Republic of Biafra by Chukwuemeka Ojukwu on May 30, 1967 and the Nigerian Civil War, which claimed 1.5 million lives. General Murtala Mohammed was murdered on February 13, 1976, in another coup led by Col. Bukar Sukar Dimka. In 1980, religious violence also claimed over four thousand lives in Zaria and Kano. Furthermore, fifty-three (53) people, primarily Christians, also died from the Kaduna crisis in 1980, while about two hundred (200) lost their lives in Katsina. In April 1991, the *Izala* sect's attempt to stop Evangelist Reinhard Bonnke from conducting a crusade in Kano led to the loss of many lives. According to the New York-based Rights Group, more than 935 people were killed in about 164 attacks linked to Boko Haram from shootings and bombings between July 2009 and 2014. Another report placed the number of deaths between 2009 and 2013 at 3000. Religious violence has been primarily responsible for bloodshed, especially in Northern Nigeria. The activity of the British to create Northern Nigeria through conquest and social and political incorporation into the dominant Islamic society resulted in groups "made up of linguistic and ethnic groups but with conflicting historical legacies." The divide between the Northern North,

dominated by Muslims, and the Southern North, dominated by Christians, have resulted in religious violence in Northern Nigeria.

Adeloye (2014: 16-18) attributed the precarious state of the country regarding bloodshed to insecurity and violence. Violence is perpetrated by the religious extremists, Boko Haram, who kill or maim people. Insecurity and violence are also responsible for the activities of armed robbers, kidnappers, human traffickers and ritual killers. Usually, every society is supposed to enact deterrent sanctions against violent acts for peace to remain, Adeloye noted, but lamented regrettably that that is not the case in Nigeria. National dailies reported a kidnappers' den that was discovered in Ibadan, where people had been killed, and which was littered with human skulls and decayed corpses. Ayandokun (2014: 56-58) recounted bloodshed that plagued the nation between April and July 2014. She listed two separate car bombs where at least 56 people were respectively killed; an attack whereby dozens of people were killed; there was an attack by suspected militants on three villages the killing of around 37 people in a bomb blast in Abuja; the killing of ten people in a red light district of Northern Nigeria's Bauchi; the killing of at least 16 soldiers in Borno state and the shooting and killing of 18 people in Kaduna. She also lamented that these reports were not exaggerations of made-up stories. According to her, the situation was worsening by the day as Nigeria was rated 100.2 under the overall worst performance by the failed states index in 2014.

Osaghae and Suberu (2005:17-20) maintained that ethno-regional federalism resulted in political tribulations that assailed Nigeria in the sixties, resulting in bloody coups, fragmentation and politicisation of military institutions. Inter-ethnic clashes in Nigeria since the late 1980s have taken many forms, and these include Tiv-Jukun clashes in Benue and Taraba States, Urhobo-Ijaw-Itsekiri clashes, Hausa-Fulani, and Yoruba and Igbo clashes. Intra-ethnic and intra-religious clashes occurred in the Aguleri-Umuleri areas of Anambra. In contrast, Ife-Modakeke in Osun State clashed because of land disputes. The clashes between Fulani herders and farmers over grazing routes and lands illustrate other inter-ethnic clashes in the nation.

In his submission, Egbetakin (2014: 80) averred that security started to diminish sharply in Nigeria since the 1980s, and bloodshed has increased since then. The checker plans the government put in place, including the operations by the Joint Task Force (JTF), Anti-Bomb Squad, Rapid

Response Squad, and Scorpion Marshal of the States, have failed to put an end to insecurity. He also noted that the introduction of vigilante groups and the call for state policing through private and public sponsorship have all ended in a fiasco, as 10 to 20 people fall into the hands of kidnappers frequently, and 60% fall to bomb blasts or straight massacres. Olayoku (2016: 62-63) stated that religious and cultural factors had hindered the symbiotic relationship between herders and farmers as the Fulani migrated more to the South. The Miyetti Allah Breeders Association of Nigeria (MACBAN) has registered its agitations and canvassed for the integration of Fulani into the communities where they settle. The communities used for grazing by the Fulani become hotbeds for bloodshed because of the adverse effects of the invasion of farmlands, assault on non-Fulani women by herders, scarcity of fresh water, cattle theft, inadequate animal health and disease control, overgrazing, and defilement of land and water by animal faeces. According to the Nigeria Watch Newsletter 2014, the north-central states of Taraba, Nasarawa, Plateau, and Benue are most affected by bloodshed due to grazing conflicts. The Fulani herders' use of modern and sophisticated weapons made the people in those communities resort to self-defence through vigilante groups. The cattle grazing conflict has existed since the beginning of agriculture. In Nigeria, colonisation, the fall of the Sokoto Caliphate and the introduction of *Jangali* (Cattle tax) marginalised and dispersed the Fulani further towards the South. The ecologically viable coastal zones were destroyed due to the continuous decimation of pasture across the Savannah. The clashes that claim lives seem to be prevalent between May and September, during the rainy season, when the Fulani return towards the North, and a time signalling the peak of crop production. Between June 2006 and May 2014, 615 violent deaths were recorded. According to Mambula's (2016:65-121) documentation of violence in Nigeria, in 2008, thirty-one (31) deaths were documented, with Anambra State having the highest number of cases (9). In 2009, eighty-three (83) deaths were recorded, with Nasarawa State having the highest number of cases (47). In 2010, thirty-nine (39) deaths were recorded, with Niger State having the highest deaths (15). In 2011, there was a meteoric rise with one hundred and sixteen (116) deaths, and Benue State had the highest number of cases (65). In 2012, there were one hundred and twenty-eight (128) deaths, with Cross River having the highest number of cases (40). In 2013, there were one hundred and fifteen (115) cases, with Benue having the

highest number (37). In 2014, there were twenty-seven (27) cases, with Taraba having the highest number of cases (10). Musa Mambula also gave a timeline of bloodshed through the activities of Boko Haram between September 2010 and September 2014, which were gathered from the pages of the Newspaper. The records can be described as horrific and disheartening.

In his research, Ojo (2016: 92) found that religion, land disputes, ethnicity, politics, election, community violence and crimes involving Muslims and Christians are the underlying causes of violent deaths between Christians and Muslims or within the same religious faith. Fundamentalism in both religions has given rise to “militant expressions”, resulting in the advocacy of self-defence to protect lives and defend their faith by Northern Nigerian Christians, one that has not gained prominence or a wider reputation than Islam. He reported that incidents of bloodshed between Christians or representations of Western culture in Nigeria received media interest and hype locally and internationally. Between June 2006 and May 2014, 11,300 victims lost their lives due to religious causes. Violent groups also attack Christians and Muslims, judging by the scale of the loss of lives. With this submission, it seems that religious conflict had played a central role in the frequency and pattern of bloodshed and perspectives towards it.

In his research on killings by security forces in Nigeria, Afeno (2016: 112) revealed that the intervention of security forces in violent incidents does more harm than good. A study shows that between June 2006 and May 2014, the intervention of security agents caused 59% of the fatalities. The more they intervene, the more people are killed. The more they intervene, the more people are killed. The study also revealed that the killings by the police are more prevalent than those by the army; these killings are more prevalent in the southern part of the country, but fatalities are more prevalent in the North. Afeno noted that security agents had exploited their constitutional authority to carry out extra-judicial and arbitrary killings in their engagement with the civilians. Notably, the JTF deployed from the Nigerian Army, Air Force, Navy, State Security Service (SSS), Police Force, Department of State Security (DSS), Immigration, and Customs Officials; applies excessive force beyond their jurisdiction they illegally arrests, detains and kills civilians at will. Afeno reported forceful extortion of bribes by the security forces and resultant killings. He added that they also responded to civil unrest, like protests and riots, and went to the extreme in

mediating peace. Security agents serve the interests of politicians or leaders in power and are never legally held responsible for their excesses. Further, corrupt practices, forceful extortion, human rights abuse, and extra-judicial killings are sometimes carried out by ill-equipped and demoralised agents. Involvement in oil bunkering and misappropriation of security funds by political executives result in an unresolved crisis in the Niger Delta. Also, they seek bribes to investigate, discontinue, or kill influential individuals. There have been outcries in the national dailies regarding the torture, maiming, and killing of innocent citizens by security operatives like the military and the police, who are supposed to protect lives. Their cruelty sparked the notable #EndSARS protests. The Special Anti-Robbery Squad's (SARS) untamed brutality on Nigerian citizens sparked public outbursts when the latter could no longer hold it. The nationwide protests gained momentum and spread from one city to another and state to state. Nigerians and the whole world, especially the victims' families, will not forget the Lekki Toll Gate massacre for a long time. At the Toll Gate, the Military personnel shot at harmless, innocent citizens fighting for a better Nigeria. It was reported that the act occurred between 6.45 pm and 9.00 pm on Tuesday, 20th October 2020. It was a calculated attempt to foil the protesters' plans, as the CCTV cameras covering the area were said to have been disabled before they opened fire on the unarmed citizens. Commenting on the incident, Osai Ojigho, the Country Director of Amnesty International, Nigeria (2021), stated that "opening fire on peaceful protesters is a violation of their rights to life, dignity, freedom and peaceful assembly. Soldiers had one intention- to kill without consequences." The person who ordered the attempt to stop the protesters in their tracks remains unnamed. There were widespread reactions from individuals, corporate bodies and the international community against this cowardly act. Investigations and court hearings were conducted, but nothing concrete has been done to the perpetrators.

According to Amnesty International (2024: 6-8), at least another twenty-four protesters were killed in Niger, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Jigawa and Borno State in another #EndBadGovernance protest that took place between 1-10 August 2024. Alao *et al* (2019: 38) decried the negative impact of violence on food security in Benue State. Also recently, over 200 people were reportedly killed in Yelewata, Guma Local Government area of Benue State. The perpetrators were reported to have used sophisticated weapons

and fuel to set houses ablaze (Odeniyi *et al*, 2025). These reviews show that religion, ethnicity, politics, ritual killing, and injustice are the leading causes of violent activities in Nigeria.

Analysis of Numbers 35:30-31

This section aims to investigate syntactical arrangements used in the *pericope* to discover the intended meaning of the Hebrew text.

Law regarding Murder, Numbers 35:30

Kāl-maKēh- nefesh l'fiy ēdiym yir'tzach et-hārotzē'ch w'ēd echād lo-yaáneh v'nefesh lāmût

Numbers 35:30: Anyone who strikes a person, the one that killed shall be murdered according to the testimony of witnesses; but no one shall die on the testimony of one witness.

Kāl is a common noun masculine singular construct meaning “all, each, every, whole, any,” joined by *maqfēf* to a verb *maKēh* a *hiphil* participle masculine singular construct from the root meaning “he struck, he smite, he slaughtered” joined by *maqfēf* to *nefesh* a common noun dual singular absolute meaning “soul, living being, person, life, breath, desire,” hence, “anyone causing to strike a living being,” connotes that God instructed that even though an offence has been committed, a grievous one at that, the offender will be at the mercy of the number of witnesses. This verb also occurs in old Aramaic, Akkadian texts. Out of the 504 occurrences, it only appears in the *niphal* once in 2 Samuel 11:15 and pual twice in Exodus 9:31, 32. The vast majority are in the *hiphil*, with some in the *hophal*. The meaning ranges from ‘hitting’ to ‘killing’. It could lead to the death penalty for striking a fellow human. It is a form of premeditated assault on a being and one that will attract God’s punishment.

According to Hodge (1995: 2), in God's judgment, many offenders should go unpunished through lack of testimony rather than for the security of reputation and life should be endangered by allowing a single witness to establish a charge against anyone.

yir'tzach is a verb *qal* imperfect third person masculine singular from meaning “he crushed, he killed, he murdered, he slayed”. The verb is used with a person as the object that received the action. Its use in the *qal* stem

implies that the act is violent enough and does not need to be expressed in the *piel* stem. The root carries the sense of ‘killing’ or ‘murdering’. Brevard S. Childs (1986:67) noted that the word originated from blood vengeance. In the Decalogue, it is used in the six commandments (Exodus 20:13, Deuteronomy 5:17). It is a prohibition against taking another person’s life by an individual or a mob (Domeris, 1997: 1188-1190). According to Phillips (1970: 83), the significance of the word is not that it defines an illegal act but that it distinctly indicates where the killing took place, which is within a covenant community. He also noted that it denotes premeditated as well as unpremeditated, including authorised killing within the community. In any homicide case, there needed to be witnesses to the act to establish guilt; one witness alone was not enough (Walvoord & Zuck, 1985:257). Janzen (2000: 277) noted that two or three witnesses were required, especially in the case of a capital crime. This implies that any act of murder is a betrayal of the covenant that God had with the Israelite community and one that must be punished if they will not incur His wrath.

The witnesses must stand as accusers against a murderer. According to the Talmud, it was considered sinful in a case of immorality for a single witness to come forward to testify alone. Also, according to Old Testament legal procedure, witnesses were required to lead in casting the first stones against the condemned (Deut. 13:9–10; Deut. 17:6–7) (Trites, 1996: 145). Even though family members of the deceased witnessed the killing of their loved ones, they cannot retaliate by taking the life of the offender or collect damages. They cannot participate in the criminal proceedings except act as witnesses. The offender, if found guilty, will be executed. He has brought about death by taking away a life which is regarded as a gift of *Yahweh*. The life force of man has its seat in the blood and cannot be taken by another man under any circumstance. So, anyone who takes what belongs to *Yahweh* by killing another must be killed by the covenant community in order to appease *Yahweh*. In this way, the ownership of man’s life is returned to Him.

Prohibition against Ransom and Manslaughter, Numbers 35:31

w'lo-tiq'chû khofer l'nefesh rotzë^ach ásher-hû räshä lämût Kiy-môt yûmät

Numbers 35:31: And you shall not take a ransom for a person who is guilty of killing; he shall be caused to die.

tiq'chû verb qal imperfect second person masculine plural from the root meaning “he took, he grasped,” hence “and you shall not take or receive.” The root in the *niphal* stem means to be carried away or removed. Cognates of the root occur in Ancient Near East Semitic languages and express the same concept of receiving, taking or accepting a gift, ransom or bribe, etc. Taking or grasping implies expressing a desire to gain control and do something, whether it is prohibited or not. The text uses it as an emphatic juridical prohibition in the volitive mood. This is indicated by the prepositive negative with the imperfect verb. The commandments issued in this way are usually universal and apply to all men at all times by divine or civil authority (Price, 2016: 141). *Kopher* a common noun, masculine singular; absolute meaning “ransom, redemption, atonement, price of a life, shrub, tree, bitumen”.

According to Elwell and Barry (1988:1821), “redemption” and “ransom” are not unrelated concepts. *Kopher* also means “a cover” or a “covering”, which was made in place of life or punishment. A ransom could be paid to redeem the life of the owner of an ox that had gored a person to death (Ex 21:30). It is used in a bad sense as a “bribe” to purchase favour (1 Samuel 12:3). A half-shekel ransom price was required by God for each Israelite at census taking to prevent a plague (30:12), and this “atonement money” was an offering to the Lord for use in the tabernacle service. A murderer could not be ransomed, and anyone who found safety in a city of refuge could not be taken back by ransom (Nm 35:31, 32). The inability to ransom life from the death penalty is reflected in the law: “Do not take ransom for the life of the murderer.” “Ransom” parallels judicial bribery in 1 Sam 12:8 and Amos 5:12 (Freedman, 1996: 651). In other words, taking ransom is equal to taking a bribe to hide the truth and malign justice. Here, capital punishment was decreed for murderers; there was no escape or rectification.

According to Richards (1996: 114), in other ancient cultures, a murderer could avoid another penalty by paying a ransom to the victim’s family, even if the act was premeditated. However, the Old Testament says, “Do not

accept a ransom from a murderer that is guilty and deserving death. The adjective is a masculine singular absolute meaning 'wicked, criminal, bad person, guilty.' He has transgressed, so he should not go scot-free (Holladay and Kohler, 1971: 347). This implies that bribery only cancels an offender's crime in man's record, it has not been rectified with the superior (God) in the covenant relationship.

In the case of premeditated murder, even the altar of Yahweh could not protect the offender from the death penalty (Exod. 21:14). The application of *lex talionis* in Leviticus 24:17–21 makes it clear that while "life for life" may only require compensation if the death of an animal is involved, it most certainly requires capital punishment if a man is killed.

In the Old Testament, *shaphak* is the root word that refers to something being poured out, shed or spilt. The word often refers to bloodshed in the context of either murder or warfare. It is used in Genesis 9:6, where murder is condemned on the basis that human beings are created in the image of God. Also, Reuben urged his brothers not to shed Joseph's blood (Gen. 37:22); Abigail warned David against killing Nabal (1 Sam. 25:31) and it is stated that to take someone's life is contempt for God and pollution of the land (Num. 35:33) (Wolf and Holmstedt, 1997: 222). T. R. Hobbs (2002: 308) noted that the expression "to shed innocent blood" is quite deuteronomic (Deut 19:10, 13; 21:8, 9; 27:25; 1 Sam 19:5; Jer 7:6; 19:4; 22:3, 17; 26:15) and that the innocent blood is not permitted to be spilt because permitting that will amount to murder. The word *ekcheo* is used to express the shedding or spilling of blood in the New Testament. Its instances in the New Testament include Matthew 23:35, Luke 11:50, Romans 3:15, Hebrews 9:22 and Revelation 16:6. It connotes taking the life of an innocent individual. According to Edersheim (1997: 49), the land is the recipient of the violent actions of murderers who shed blood in the Old Testament. Therefore, the blood shed by a murderer's hand could not be covered up; until the blood of him that had shed it quietened its voice.

Inference from Numbers 35:30-31

From the pericope, the rejection of compensation for homicide in Numbers 35:30-31 reflects a high regard for the sanctity of human life. God did not intend reckless taking of lives but rather that life be respected and preserved. Premeditated killing, including assassination, seems to be implied here. The custom was rooted in the ordinance of God, which required

a life for a life in any case of intentional homicide (Gen. 9:6). Unfortunately, the intent of the law, to impress upon humanity the sacredness of human life, has sometimes been greatly distorted, leading to blood feuds. Shedding of human blood and adultery could be atoned for only by capital punishment, as offences against life's sacredness (Gen. 9:5, 6; Lev. 20:10; Num. 35:33), hence the concept of life ransomed by a life given. Also, the sixth commandment states categorically, *You shall not kill* (Exod. 20:13). When life becomes cheap, all other values diminish; the meaning of being human is lost. Killing reduces human existence to the level of beasts of prey. Blood spilt in violence calls out to God from the ground (Gen. 4:10–12) (Guenther, 1998: 92). God intends that human life be respected and preserved.

Perspectives on Sanctity of Human Life

Engelhardt, Spicker and Bayertzed (1996: xii-xiii) submitted that Sanctity of life and human dignity are related terms with religious roots. Likewise, the sanctity of life is regarded as a moral principle, meaning freedom from injury. Human dignity is related to the *imago Dei*, meaning that each human has an inherent dignity that should be exempt from human interference. The principle that human life is inviolable and holy comes into play when some bioethical decisions are made. This principle is extensively argued when decisions on abortion, intensive care, terminating treatments and euthanasia are considered. Preserving human life is the highest duty of the medical profession because life is precious.

Gitari (1997: 21-22) stated that every human being created in God's image possesses an intrinsic dignity that requires respect and honour, not elimination or exploitation. Such an individual has the right to carry out his/her civic responsibilities without fear or threat. Bloodshed has been rampaging the world because of envy, strife, and a lack of respect for human life. Also, Harigovind (2013:1-2) posited that the sanctity of life and the value of human life are universal when science and the law interact. The writer admitted that the dignity of human life had been a legal doctrine right from the creation account where God made man with unique features and prominent among the creations. Also, religions like Christianity, Hinduism, Buddhism and Islam uphold that the sanctity of life is vital for both humans and other living creatures. Under human rights jurisprudence, human dignity has been upheld, especially in abortion, euthanasia and human experimentation cases. At first, Greek theologians

like Nietzsche and Plato did not place a high premium on human dignity until the introduction of scholasticism into the natural law jurisprudence. The academic school regarded all men as members of the same spiritual humanity.

A questionnaire was distributed and analysed to ascertain the understanding of the causes of bloodshed in Nigeria among one hundred and twenty-three respondents. Ritual killing was rated first with a mean score of 3.5366, representing 88.4 per cent. Next to the first-rated item is murder, with a mean difference of 0.04 from the first, representing 1 per cent. The third and fourth rated items (assassination and manslaughter) are close, with a mean difference of 0.05, representing 1.25 per cent. Self-defence is rated least. There is a mean difference of 0.89 between the first and fifth rated items, representing 22 per cent. The average mean of all the respondents on the causes of bloodshed is 3.26, which is 81.5 per cent. The standard deviation suggests that the respondents' opinions for the first four items are homogeneous. The discussion of findings shows that ritual killing was rated first, which shows that it is the most frequent occurrence of bloodshed in Nigeria. Respondents believe that the rate at which people are kidnapped and killed to harvest their body parts for rituals is alarming compared to the rate of murder, assassination, manslaughter and killing in self-defence. The table shows that killing in self-defence is the least occurring form of bloodshed in Nigeria. This implies that there is little or no regard for human life among perpetrators, which is against the Biblical and legal laws regarding the dignity of human life.

Bloodshed as a Negation of the Sanctity of Human Life in Nigeria

Blood is the fluid circulating in a vertebrate animal's heart, arteries, capillaries and veins, carrying nourishment and oxygen to all body parts. Because of its importance, it is the life of a human being and is therefore forbidden as food for another man by God. Its importance is in its sacredness, designation as the essence of life and a means of atonement. To shed blood is a form of brutal human sacrifice that God frowns at. As expressed in the Bible, it is sacred, reserved for God and can only be used during sacrificial atonement. Otherwise, it becomes a curse if it is wanted only shed.

The prohibition against consuming animal flesh from which the blood had not been drained may have been to oppose a cruel, barbaric custom of eating

live animals or those whose blood is still warm. Perhaps it implies the future importance of blood for sacrificial purposes. Human bloodshed is forbidden because human beings are created in the image of God. When God demanded a reckoning for the blood of a human being, he took human life into his protection and established an intimate connection between blood and life. In this way, God hope to arrest the prevalence of murder that emerged when Cain killed his brother, Abel.

Shedding innocent blood in Nigeria occurs through ritual killing, murder, land dispute, armed robbery, and abortion (Ayandokun 2014, Olayoku 2016, Mambula 2016, Taft and Haken 2015, Falola 1998). Reports of such murders are prevalent on the pages of newspapers and the electronic media. The worrisome note is that perpetrators belong to one religious group or the other. There have been reports of ritual killings in Soka area of Ibadan and in Ogun State where houses littered with human body parts, skeletons and imprisoned men and women were discovered (Ogah and Uban, 2024: 7). People are being killed, lives are desecrated, and body parts mutilated and removed for sinister purposes such as the quest for money, power, position, fame or political victory. It is doubly tragic that the perpetrators of the heinous acts hardly spare the members of their families and relatives in these killings.

The disregard for life and human dignity is a blatant disobedience to the commandment of God, who created man in His image and places a high premium on life. Religion is supposed to unite human beings and entrench God's commandment against bloodshed. Religious sentiments have caused many crises that have resulted in bloodshed in Nigeria. The political class had hijacked the situation to further their campaigns and agendas. The threat of religious agitation must be managed rightly, especially between Christianity and Islam. The religious leaders must recognise Nigeria's religious diversity and the dangers that ego, selfishness and sentiment pose to the nation's security.

Further, this researcher believes that scholars across religious divides should be intellectually engaged so that fanatics and extremists can be cautioned. This engagement can help to address the manipulation of unlearned adherents who are being used as instruments of destruction of human lives. If the prominent religions claim that they are religions of peace, they should demonstrate it by tolerating one another.

If the rate at which blood is shed in Nigeria is reduced drastically, then Nigerian citizens have a role to play. All media that can lead to provocation and result in the taking of another's life must be removed. Nigerian citizens must recognise and maintain the sanctity of human life, peacefully co-exist with others and tolerate all. This remedy should start from the home. Children and youths who grew up in poverty without care, inadequate parenting, abuse, exposure to violence from a tender age, volatile existence and a broken country will engage in bloodshed. Nigeria seems to be a society that trains young people for social vices but not for selfless leadership. Therefore, the home must be given adequate care, where the parents and the children are responsible and possess good morals.

Conclusion

In this paper, an overview and perspectives about bloodshed and sanctity of human life have been discussed with an analysis of Numbers 35:30-31 in order to respond to the menace of disregard for human lives. The commandment by God from the text is not a vendetta or a yardstick for serial murderers. It is a way that God put in place to ensure the sanctity of the lives He had created in His image. The application of the text can adequately resolve the crisis of shedding innocent blood that has plagued the nation over the years, and which seems uncontrollable. If the citizens are law-abiding, tolerate one another in a multi-ethnic group setting like ours, live in harmony despite religious differences, and avoid provoking one another through speech and actions, bloodshed will reduce drastically. Cultural values and proper ethics should be entrenched into the fabrics of the society tailored towards recognizing the sanctity of human lives, and building a society where justice and fairness are maintained, and everyone is treated equally. Only a society whose citizens are law-abiding, tolerant and showing attributes of love, concern, care, compassion and tolerance for one another, irrespective of colour, class, ethnic group, and religion, can recognise the sanctity of human lives. An ideal society is not hindered or segregated by barriers, prejudices and preferences. Individuals should be subjected to the same law without partiality or special legal privileges to some. Every citizen should be able to exercise their fundamental human rights and be free from discrimination or harm. Citizens are encouraged to use legitimate means to protect themselves by recruiting guards and vigilante groups, installing CCTV cameras, and learning military or

combatant skills to protect themselves. They are discouraged from taking the law into their own hands.

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